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Abstract

The paper describes a relatively new terrestrial remote sensing technique for deformation monitoring: ground-based SAR interferometry (GBSAR). It provides an introductory overview of this technique, making a short review of the most relevant GBSAR studies published in the literature. Then the basics of GBSAR interferometry for deformation measurement are outlined. Deriving deformation estimates from the GBSAR images is often not a straightforward process: a brief description of the GBSAR data processing chain developed by the authors is provided. Finally, the paper concisely discusses the main advantages and limitations of the technique.

Keywords

SAR • Interferometry • Terrestrial • Deformation • Monitoring

27.1 Introduction

In the last years GBSAR, a radar-based terrestrial remote sensing system (Tarchi and Rudolf 1999), has gained an increasing interest as a deformation monitoring tool. It consists on a radar sensor that emits/receives a burst of microwaves, repeating this operation while the sensor is moving along a rail track. The imaging capability is achieved by exploiting the Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) technique. The GBSAR is based on a coherent system, which measures not only the amplitude but also the phase of the received radar signal. The phase can be exploited to derive information on the deformation and topography of the measured scene. The main application is deformation monitoring, where the high sensitivity to deformations, the long range (up to several km) and the imaging capability, which allows the system to perform a vast number of

measurements, are interesting characteristics that make the GBSAR system complementary to other deformation measurement techniques.

Most of the GBSAR studies published in the literature concern landslide monitoring, where the GBSAR can offer good performances with respect to other measurement techniques, such as total stations or Terrestrial Laser Scanners (TLS). Several authors use a GBSAR for slope monitoring in a continuous mode, i.e. leaving the instrument installed in situ during the whole monitoring period (Pieraccini et al. 2002; Leva et al. 2003; Tarchi et al. 2003; Herrera et al. 2009). Reference (Luzi 2010a) describes a discontinuous monitoring experiment based on artificial reflectors. This approach is usually appropriate to monitor slow or very slow displacement phenomena. Reference (Crosetto et al. 2009) explores the possibility of monitoring a rock fall using GBSAR. Other interesting references include dam monitoring (Tarchi and Rudolf 1999), the monitoring of manmade structures (Tarchi et al. 2000; Luzi et al. 2010b), urban subsidence (Pipia and Fabregas 2007), glacier displacements (Luzi et al. 2007; Riesen et al. 2011), volcano slopes (Casagli et al. 2009), snow covered surfaces (Martinez-Vazquez and Fortuny-Guasch 2008; Luzi et al. 2009)

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and monitoring slopes in open pit mines (Mecatti and Macaluso 2010).

Several GBSAR systems have been described in the literature in the last decade. A thorough review of such systems is available in (Monserrat et al. 2014).

27.2 GBSAR Interferometry Fundamentals

This section recalls some important aspects of GBSAR interferometry for deformation measurement. We start by briefly mentioning the main characteristics of a GBSAR system. For this purpose we make explicit reference to a GBSAR implementation, the IBIS-L system by Ingegneria dei Sistemi SpA (Bernardini et al. 2007). The IBIS-L system consists of four main components: the radar head (sensor module), which has two antennas, one for emitting and one for receiving the backscattered signal; the rail along which the radar head is moving during data acquisition; a portable computer to control the system and storing the acquired data; and a power supply module. The system exploits two main techniques. An appropriate range sampling is obtained by using the Continuous Wave-Frequency Stepped technique, while the capability to resolve objects in the cross-range direction is based on the SAR technique. The IBIS-L system works in Ku-band, with wavelength of approximately 17.6 mm, and can acquire data up to a range of 4 km with a maximum range resolution of 0.5 m. In the cross-range direction, it has a maximum angular resolution of 4.4 mrad (i.e. 4.4 m at 1 km): the pixel footprint increases linearly with the sensor to target distance. The area covered by a typical IBIS-L survey has roughly a triangular shape, with an aperture of approximately 30°–35°. This aperture can however vary by using antennas with different gains.

A full 2D image is derived using the data obtained by displacing the sensor along the whole rail. For each image pixel the system acquires a complex number, the In-phase and Quadrature (I and Q) components of the received echo, from which the signal phase ϕ and amplitude A can be derived:

$$\phi = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{Q}{I} \right); \quad A = \sqrt{I^2 + Q^2}$$

The amplitude is mainly used for interpretation of the image scene and the study of backscattering characteristics of the monitored area, while the phase can be exploited for deformation measurement, which is the subject of this paper, or for digital elevation model generation. Let's consider a deformation measurement scenario, taking the phases ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 of two homologous pixels (i.e. pixels that correspond to the same target) from two images acquired at different times:

$$\phi_1 = \phi_{geom-1} + \phi_{scat-1} = \frac{4 \cdot \pi \cdot R_1}{\lambda} + \phi_{scat-1}$$

$$\phi_2 = \phi_{geom-2} + \phi_{scat-2} = \frac{4 \cdot \pi \cdot R_2}{\lambda} + \phi_{scat-2}$$

where R_1 and R_2 are the sensor to target distances at each acquisition, ϕ_{scat} is the phase shift generated during the interaction between the microwaves and the target, λ the wavelength of the emitted signal, and the factor 4π is related to the two way path, radar-target-radar. The interferometric phase $\Delta\phi_{21}$, which is the main GBSAR observable, is given by:

$$\Delta\phi_{21} = \phi_2 - \phi_1 = \frac{4 \cdot \pi \cdot (R_2 - R_1)}{\lambda} + (\phi_{scat-2} - \phi_{scat-1})$$

If the phase shift components ϕ_{scat-2} and ϕ_{scat-1} remain constant between two acquisitions (i.e. their variation over time is negligible), $\Delta\phi_{21}$ is directly related to the distance difference ($R_2 - R_1$) and hence to the target displacement. This corresponds to an ideal situation, because, in practice, there are at least three other terms that play a role in GBSAR interferometry:

$$\Delta\phi_{21} = \frac{4 \cdot \pi \cdot (R_2 - R_1)}{\lambda} + (\phi_{atm-2} - \phi_{atm-1}) + \phi_{noise} + 2 \cdot k \cdot \pi$$

where ϕ_{noise} is the component related to $(\phi_{scat-2} - \phi_{scat-1})$ and other noise sources; $(\phi_{atm-2} - \phi_{atm-1})$ is the component due to the atmospheric effects during the two image acquisitions; k is an integer value; and $2 \cdot k \cdot \pi$ is due to the fact that $\Delta\phi_{21}$ is wrapped, i.e. bounded in the range $[-\pi, \pi]$. This is the main equation of GBSAR for deformation measurement, which will be discussed later in this paper.

27.3 GBSAR Data Processing Chain

This section describes the main steps of the GBSAR processing chain for deformation measurement developed by the authors.

- Image co-registration. Interferometry can only be performed if the images are co-registered, i.e. pixels with same location in the two images match the same ground footprint. Different co-registration algorithms are described in (Monserrat 2012).
- Interferogram and coherence generation. From the stack of N co-registered images, the interferograms and the associated coherence images are generated.